

DIRECTIONS OF TRAINING TO SELF-ASSESSMENT FOR PUPILS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, there are directions for teaching students of preschool educational organizations to self-assessment, children's assessment activity, its specific aspects, opportunities to ensure the objectivity of the assessment, and the structure of self-assessment. held. This article serves as an important methodical resource for the pedagogical community, educators, parents and researchers.*

Keywords: *self-assessment, skills, children, educators, requirements, activity, training, assessment subject, assessment process.*

Today, one of the socio-pedagogical problems facing the preschool education process is the formation of elementary skills of self-development in children. Theoretical approaches in the field of formation of the initial skills of self-development among pupils of preschool educational organizations have not been sufficiently developed. However, the child's self-esteem is of particular importance.

It is important to form a child's personality and realize his potential in preschool educational organizations. In order to develop ambition in a child, it is necessary to create conditions for his self-evaluation. Because the child seeks to develop only after he clearly knows his capabilities. The analysis of scientific sources on self-assessment of a person shows that self-assessment first of all requires a clear knowledge of one's capabilities. As a result of assessment, the child has the opportunity to realize himself.

Our observations showed that educators do not pay attention to creating favorable conditions for children's self-evaluation. They are not asked questions that give them the opportunity to evaluate themselves. Methods that create favorable conditions for children's self-evaluation are almost not addressed. Most children rate themselves extremely low or very high. Educators do not think about the formation of adequate assessment skills in children. Often, children are unable to show their potential because they think "I can't do that", "I can't do it". In most cases, educators use the method of coercion. As a result, children's self-confidence is decreasing. Self-assessment skills in children should begin at a very young age, from the day they enter preschool. Because the process of preschool education is the first stage of preparing children for social life and social relations.

In the process of justifying the fact that the formation of self-assessment skills in children is a methodological necessity, we were able to justify the insufficient development of methodological instruments that allow the formation of this skill.

Formation of self-assessment skills in children should become a component of the pedagogical process organized in preschool educational organizations. For this, educators are required to know the components and pedagogical features of self-assessment activities well. It is known that self-assessment has always been interpreted as a component of pedagogical problems. In the pedagogical encyclopedia, the concept of "self-assessment" is described as follows: self-

assessment is a concept that expresses the student's objective attitude to his capabilities, abilities, and personal qualities. Self-evaluation is an expression of a person's cognitive activity, attitude to surrounding people and material existence. Self-esteem is a unique set of management of personal human relations in society. In theoretical approaches to psychology, special attention is paid to the psychological interpretation of the assessment. The content and essence of self-assessment is an activity aimed at opening up the child's personal and psychological possibilities.

The activity of each child in the training process, the level of knowledge acquisition is evaluated by the teacher. This assessment is expressed through the teacher's attitude. In pre-school education organizations, the assessment given to the child by the educator consists of a description. That is, the educator evaluates the child's behavior by expressing his/her attitude towards it.

The teacher's assessment of the child requires an objective response to his actions. The child's behavior should be in accordance with the requirements for preschool education. The assessment covers the skills acquired by the children as well as the description given to their personal qualities. Experts have shown that there are aspects of assessment based on external and internal reflection. The internal reflexive evaluation is given by the child himself. It shows the child's point of view and self-image. In the educational systems of developed countries, special attention is paid to the child's self-assessment, and determining its authenticity based on analysis is one of the important tasks of the pedagogue. Educators should know well which principles a child follows in self-evaluation. It is important for them to regularly analyze the child's self-assessment and check its objectivity, accuracy, compatibility with the educator's assessment.

Educators should pay attention to the following when forming self-assessment skills in children. They are: accuracy, adequacy, completeness of assessment. The child's self-assessment determines the quality of his activity. Children's assessments of themselves are mostly subjective. In order to ensure the objectivity of this assessment, the educator is required to conduct interviews and question-and-answer sessions with children.

Children are able to objectively evaluate themselves, realizing the essence of their actions. The child's self-assessment activities are carried out in the following directions:

1. Children evaluate their activities together with their peers. In this case, self-assessment becomes more objective.
2. The child evaluates his own activity independently. This assessment will be subjective in nature.

Educators should use the following methods to develop self-assessment skills in children:

- joint selection of evaluation models;
- collaborative determination of assessment forms;
- formation of a collective opinion in a group of children;
- expanding children's opportunities to evaluate each other and themselves.

Children's collective assessment of their activities is the basis for the formation of self-assessment skills. In order to successfully develop self-assessment skills in children, educators should create situations for them to analyze their own activities and perform exercises that identify their interests.

The formation of children's independent self-assessment skills is carried out in the course of training. Their self-assessment gives an idea of their level of development. A child's self-evaluation is an expression of his attitude towards his personal qualities and actions.

Self-assessment allows children to be effectively prepared for future educational activities. Experts were able to identify the components of self-evaluation. Including:

- estimated goal;
- ideal "I";
- mental state;
- self-similarity;
- standard;
- socio-cultural examples;
- personal point of view;
- control locus.

Self-awareness is the process of evaluating oneself based on comparison with others. According to A.I.Lipkina, the spiritual image of a child is manifested through acquired personal qualities.

A.I.Lipkina and L.A.Rybakov emphasized that the child's self-evaluation process consists of two stages.

1. Self-esteem is manifested in the child's external actions.
2. Self-assessment represents the internal state of the child's personality.

Only when the child begins to think critically about himself, he achieves an objective assessment of himself. The self-assessment process requires the following mutually enriching activities:

- to find out that his assessment corresponds to the opinions of his teacher, parents and teammates about him;
- the teacher's ability to clearly imagine the attitude of the child towards his assessment;
- cooperative assessment of children in the group;
- evaluation of the work performed by him;
- making corrections to the assessment given to oneself by comparing it with the assessment of the group mates;
- to compare the evaluations given by the educator to the works of himself and his teammates.

As a result, children have a clear idea about the similar works of each other. The concept of evaluation and criticism are mutually exclusive. The critical point of view formed in children is the basis for their objective self-evaluation.

A child's self-evaluation is formed on the basis of the following skills:

- formation of children's ability to determine the subject of assessment;
- the ability to create a clear picture of assessment actions;
- the ability to enter situations necessary for assessment.

Educators are required to know and regularly use the tools, methods and methods of forming these skills in children.

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